

Subsequent decomposition of the glycidonitrile (III) with anhydrous aluminium chloride⁷ furnished 4-isopropyl-1-cyclohexen-1-carboxaldehyde (I) in 60% yield.

The identity of the synthesised product with the natural aldehyde was established through melting points of its semicarbazone and 2,4-dinitrophenylhydrazone derivatives and U.V. spectrum data.

EXPERIMENTAL*

4-Isopropylcyclohexanone (II).—4-Isopropylcyclohexen-2-one, obtained from 4-isopropylanisole by the modified Birch reduction according to the directions detailed by Sukh Dev⁹, was reduced over Pd-C catalyst to furnish 4-isopropylcyclohexanone (II) as a colorless oil, b.p. 110°/30 mm; n_D^{25} 1.4550. (Found: C, 77.20; H, 11.40. Calc. for $C_9H_{16}O$: C, 77.09; H, 11.50%). The 2,4-DNP formed yellow-orange plates from ethanol, m.p. 120° (lit.¹⁰ reported m.p. 119-21°). (Found: N, 17.40. Calc. for $C_{15}H_{20}O_4N_4$: N, 17.49%).

6-Isopropyl-1-oxaspiro-(2,5)octan-2-carbonitrile (III).—A mixture of 4-isopropylcyclohexanone (II) (10 g., 0.07 *M*) and chloroacetonitrile (6 g., 0.09 *M*) was placed in a three-necked flask, fitted with a mercury-sealed stirrer, an addition funnel, and a reflux condenser having a calcium chloride guard tube. To this was added, with continuous stirring and under nitrogen atmosphere, a solution of potassium butoxide⁶ (prepared from 3 g., 0.077 g. atom of potassium metal in 65 ml of butanol⁶). The temperature was maintained at 15-20° during the addition. The stirring was continued for another 15 hrs. at room temperature. The solvent was removed under reduced pressure up to a maximum bath temperature of 50°. To the residue were added ether and water. The ethereal layer was separated and the aqueous layer extracted four times with ether. The combined ethereal extract was washed with water and dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate. The solvent was removed and the remaining oil was fractionated to yield 12 g. (90%) of 6-isopropyl-1-oxaspiro-(2,5)octan-2-carbonitrile (III) at 115-17°/5-6 mm; n_D^{20} , 1.4695. (Found: C, 73.58; H, 9.67; N, 7.60. $C_{11}H_{17}ON$ requires C, 73.70; H, 9.56; N, 7.81%).

4-Isopropyl-1-cyclohexen-1-carboxaldehyde [($\pm$)-Phellandral] (I).—A mixture of 6-isopropyl-1-oxaspiro-(2,5)octan-2-carbonitrile (III) (6 g., 0.073 *M*) in 250 ml of dry ether and aluminium chloride (27 g., 0.438 *M*) was allowed to stand at room temperature for 1 hour. Ice-cold water was then cautiously added. The ethereal layer was separated and the aqueous layer extracted with ether. The combined ethereal phase was washed with water and dried. After removal of the solvent, the residual oil was vacuum-distilled to afford 3.2 g. (60%) of 4-isopropyl-1-cyclohexen-1-carboxaldehyde (I) as a colorless oil, b.p. 111-16°/7-8 mm; n_D^{20} 1.4889 (lit.¹¹ recorded n_D^{20} 1.4903); λ_{max}^{alc} 230.0 m μ (log ϵ , 4.1) (lit.¹¹ reported λ_{max}^{alc} 228.5 m μ ; log ϵ , 4.27). (Found: C, 78.40; H, 10.49. Calc. for $C_{10}H_{16}O$: C, 78.89; H, 10.59%).

* Melting and boiling points are uncorrected. Microanalyses by Drs. Weiler and Strauss, Oxford.

9. This *Journal*, 1956, 33, 541.

10., Heilbron and Bunbury, "Dictionary of Organic Compounds", 1953, Vol. III, p. 113.

11. Cooke and Macbeth, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1938, 1408.

The aldehyde (I) gave orange-red 2,4-DNP., m.p. 198° (Gillespie *et al.*⁵ reported m.p. 198°). (Found: N, 16.57. Calc. for $C_{16}H_{20}O_4N_4$: N, 16.86%).

The *semicarbazone* was prepared in the usual way and crystallised from ethyl acetate, m.p. 200° (Gillespie *et al.*⁵ recorded m.p. 200°). (Found: N, 19.63. Calc. for $C_{11}H_{19}ON_3$: N, 20.10%).

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